

Guidelines for headline coding - v4

Step 1: Setup

- Create a **COPY** of this spreadsheet:
<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1w5tf6rj5HxyokYVJMS916bDwyFAMUA5fweY60FYdIdM/edit?usp=sharing>
- Name the spreadsheet “YourName_coding_v4” (replace YourName with your first and last name, ie. AnnaLieb_coding_v4)
- Do NOT look at the labels that other students have worked on, even if it is in the shared google folder.
- Read the “Task Definition” blurb below.

Task Definition

News article headlines can shape the ways that people perceive current events and understand the world around them. The purpose of this task is to learn more about how article headlines frame news related to critical race theory. We will be using a set of predefined labels to organize our analysis of news headlines.

Since this is an “issue framing” project, nuances in language and word choice can be very important. Your interpretations of the headlines should be guided by the main ideas that stand out in each headline. As you make labeling judgements, you should be guided by your first impression of the headline. **Consider that a headline might belong to one of the categories *implicitly*, without direct reference to exact words provided in the label definition.**

For each headline in your spreadsheet (“YourName_coding_v4”), you will be filling in the “actor”, “action”, “action direction,” and “headline stance” columns based on your best judgment. Steps 2-5 below will guide you through this process. Please carefully read the definitions for each of the predefined labels in each step. Please use your best judgment to choose **one primary label** for each headline. If you feel that the article does not follow any of the following labels, then you may select the “None of the above / other” field.

- Perform Steps 2-5 below for each of the 50 headlines in the spreadsheet.

Step 2: Identify key “actor(s)” in the headline

Note: The purpose of this category is to identify a central “who?” in the headline. The actor can either be the one taking action (subject) or the one receiving action (object) in the headline.

Assign the headline to one of the following labels:

Key actor label	Actor’s primary role	Examples
Educational practitioner	deliver instruction to students	schools, universities, school districts, teachers, professors, school administration
Political influencer	represent the political interests and/or policy preferences of the electorate	Governor, school board, political commentator, the president, political figures
Impacted actor	participate in the school system without direct influence over policies or educational practices	Students, parents, voters
None/other	Does not fit any of the other categories	

Step 3: Identify key “action(s)” in the headline

Assign the headline to one of the following labels:

Key action label	Examples
Reporting on protest / speaking out	voicing concerns, protesting, public demonstrations, debate at public meetings
Reporting on elections	electing representatives to public office, political figures campaigning, voting
Reporting on threats / extent of CRT itself	teaching CRT, learning CRT, spread of CRT in schools, influencing the quality of education, posing a cultural/social/moral threat, limiting personal rights or civil liberties
Reporting on policy & legal actions	Imposing bans, passing legislation, implementing a school/district/state policy, filing a lawsuit, school curriculum policy
None/other	

Note for Steps 4 and 5: The “**action direction**” label describes how the news events *objectively impact* CRT. Meanwhile, the “**headline stance**” label describes how the headline’s language may be *biased* towards one stance on CRT.

For example, consider the following headline: “Florida bans critical race theory from classrooms.” For this headline, **action direction = anti-CRT** because the ban would prevent teaching CRT in classrooms. However, in this case, **headline stance = neutral** because the headline does not reveal a strong journalistic bias for or against CRT.

Step 4: Identify the action direction

Assign the headline to one of the following labels:

Action direction label	Description
anti-CRT	The headline reports on actions that restrict teaching CRT, actions taken to speak out against CRT, or any other anti-CRT actions.
defending CRT	The headline reports on actions that defend teaching CRT, or reports on actions taken to speak out in support of CRT
neutral	The headline does not clearly identify an action, or the action does not make change in either direction (neither for or against CRT).

Step 5: Identify the headline’s stance

Assign the headline to one of the following labels:

Headline stance label	Description
anti-CRT	The headline appears to favor CRT bans and/or make alarmist claims about threats posed by CRT
defending CRT	The headline appears to support CRT and/or oppose restrictions on CRT-related curricula
neutral	The headline is impartial. It reports on news events without favoring one viewpoint or the other.